

Repeat Breeding in Cattle and Buffalo

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Abstract

The presence of a sizable number of repeat breeder cows is one of the most significant loss-causing reproductive issues in dairy cattle that are now prominent at the field level. Repeat breeders have a significant negative impact on both productivity and the economy. Despite being quite critical, this ailment can be treated and controlled properly to some extent. The goal of this article is to provide some clarity on Repeat Breeder Syndrome, including its potential causes and treatment options.

Introduction

A cow or buffalo that has had artificial insemination (A.I.) performed three or more times continuously to a fertile bull or with the semen of a fertile bull yet has not given birth is considered a repeat breeder if it has a normal or nearly normal estrous cycle and oestrus period, has been bred at least once, is free of palpable abnormalities, and has given birth at least once before.

Causes And Their Management

Anomalies or segmental aplasia of the oviduct, uterus, cervix, and vagina are the most common **genetic or congenital anatomical malformations of the genital tract**. Due to this, the sperm and ovum are unable to unite, which results in ineffective fertilization.

A greater proportion of ova with a defective chromosome number, genetic mutation, abnormalities of the mesonephric ducts, testicular aplasia, post-ovulatory aging of ova that results in fertilization failure or polyspermy and early embryonic death, and aging of spermatozoa before or after ejaculation into a female are examples of **genetic, congenital, or acquired defects of the ova, spermatozoa, or early zygote**.

Anovulatory heat and delayed ovulation: A cow can be inseminated twice or three times, spaced

out by 12 hours, in cases of delayed ovulation. On the ninth or tenth day of the oestrus, the ovaries must be checked for the corpus luteum. Anovulatory heat occurs when the corpus luteum is absent from the ovary. GnRH analogs or hCG can be administered during insemination as a form of therapy to encourage ovulation.

Early embryonic death within 16 days after A.I.

The cow enters heat at the typical estrous cycle length when embryonic mortality occurs within 16 days of the cycle, or before Maternal Recognition of Pregnancy (MRP) (18-22 days). Causes of embryonic death include external factors like stress, malnutrition, extreme weather, and climatic conditions, like summer; Maternal factors like progesterone deficiency, uterine infection, etc., Embryonic factors like chromosomal abnormalities and Genetic factors. Premature embryonic death is also brought on by subclinical uterine infections. Systemic or intrauterine antibiotic treatment is advised for this. The most common treatment in practice is to do pre-AI antibiotic treatment or post-AI antibiotic treatment. For this, 10 lakh IU penicillin or 1gm. Streptopenicillin should be dissolved in 20-30 ml. of distilled water. Some veterinarians employ 200 mg of gentamicin in 30 ml of distilled water or 250 mg of ampicillin and cloxacillin (5ml). Intrauterine infusion of 1% Lugol's iodine can be done by using a volume of 150 ml of 1% Lugol's iodine infused into the uterus of the repeat breeder animal at 6 hours pre-or post-service. Pre-AI therapy should be administered 5 to 6 hours before AI, and post-AI therapy should be administered 3 to 6 hours following AI. Parenteral antibiotics (preferably streptopenicillin 2.5 gm.) should be given on day 4 and day 10 because the zygote comes to the uterus on day 4 and zona hatching and nidation of the embryo occur around day 10; so the antibiotics enter into the uterine fluid around these periods and controls the infection. Embryonic mortality can occur due to heat stress, so the inseminated cow should be kept in a cool place or shed for 15 days after insemination. Water cooling and having easy access to water are also quite beneficial.

Progesterone deficiency

Corpus luteum is the source of progesterone. Pregnancy failure occurs if there is inadequate progesterone, either because it is not fully produced or because it is not acting properly. Progesterone should be given to repeat breeder cows with a luteal deficit 3 to 5 days after insemination and should be continued for a variable length of 2 to 3 weeks to increase the likelihood of conception. Administration of hCG (2000 I.U. IM or 1000 I.U. I/V) 5 days after oestrus induces ovulation of the dominant follicle of the first wave and formation of an accessory corpus luteum which increases the plasma progesterone level. It lowers the rate of embryonic death in this way. It gives better results than progesterone administration. Administration of GnRH analog (Buserelin 10 µg. or 2.5 ml) on day 11 after insemination, reduces embryonic mortality. It is believed that the main effect of GnRH is not autotrophic like hCG but it reduces the oestradiol

concentration resulting in a decline in PGF2 alpha release during the critical period of early pregnancy. This gives the embryo more time to make interferon tau or bovine trophoblastic protein.

Deficiency of oxytocin

The lack of tonicity of the uterus in an estrous animal may be due to a deficiency of oxytocin. These animals may pass large quantities of urine when examined rectally. Following insemination, 30–50 IU of oxytocin should be administered intramuscularly.

Poor management

Animals should not be excited 15 minutes before, during, or 15 minutes after AI. As a result of the release of adrenaline brought on by excitement, oxytocin, which is necessary for the transfer of sperm, functions less effectively. After AI, the clitoris in cattle should be gently rubbed two to three times. This helps in sperm transport and ovulation. Cold water should be poured on the back of the animal after AI which causes abdominal muscle contraction and in turn of uterine muscles and thus, helps in sperm transport. Fifteen minutes of rest is necessary after AI so that the sperm can reach the utero-tubal junction. The owner should be advised to examine the mucosa of the vulvar lips of the animal daily for the "next three days" to notice any pus-flakes, which is an indication of first or second-degree endometritis such cases should be treated appropriately in the next cycle. Proper thawing of frozen semen and AI should be done within a few minutes after thawing. Proper insemination technique should be followed to deposit the semen just after the anterior end of the cervix or in the body of the uterus otherwise it will cause trauma to the genital tract.

Deficiency of Energy

If deficiency of energy is suspected, 20% dextrose intravenous should be given 1 to 2 hours before AI. The animal should be in a positive energy balance. Under-feeding of energy can result in anovulatory disorder, delayed ovulation, and embryonic mortality. The concentrate feed must contain a mineral mixture at a 2% level. Energy deficiency affects fertility in two ways. First through the GnRH system and the second through metabolic regulators of ovarian function. FSH secretion is not only largely affected by nutrition but LH secretion is also affected in negatively energy-balanced animals resulting in delayed ovulation, anovulation, or early embryonic death. The circulating concentrations of glucose, insulin and insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) are lower in cows that are in negative energy balance than in fully fed animals while the concentration of non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA) is higher in negatively energy-balanced animals. All of these alter the gonadotrophin secretion affecting follicle development. Some studies indicate that NEFA has a direct toxic effect on follicles and oocytes.

Crude Protein

The high level of crude protein (CP) in the diet hurts the conception rate. Feeding of the high level of

rumen degradable protein (RDP) leads, to an increase in circulating concentrations of ammonia and urea. In consequence, abnormally high concentrations of urea and ammonia reach the uterus, where they may be toxic to spermatozoa or adversely affect the uterine function and reduce the embryo's survival rate. In addition, abnormally high circulating concentrations of urea may also hurt the hypothalamic-pituitary axis. 20 % dietary Crude Protein Dry Matter increases the incidence of RFM, dystocia, and postpartum metritis as compared to a 13 % level. Interestingly, a small improvement occurs when undegraded rumen protein is present in the diet by neutralizing the effect of RDP. Soybean meal, fish meal, etc. have a high proportion of undegradable protein while the protein in silage and barley is degradable. Therefore, it can be concluded that high-level feeding of protein should be avoided for maintaining the fertility of the cow.

Conclusion

Of course, animals with genetic and anatomical defects are needed to be culled but Repeat Breeding can be managed to a satisfactory level by improving managerial practices. Animal management is yet of concern in India as there is a very less number of organized dairy farms. Farmers can keep very few animals and due to economic shortcomings or some other negligence, the animals are not being managed properly. Farmers should be educated about the need for proper management and care of dairy animals and how these can impact their economic health also. Practices of hygiene, heat detection, vaccination, nutrition, etc. should be taught to the animals for better management so that various ailments leading to conditions like Repeat breeding can be prevented and the health and production of animals can be improved.

